

Supplementary Table 5: Performance in the ADNI validation dataset with classifiers *K-Nearest-Neighbor (KNN)* and *BayesNet Naives (NB)*.

Classifier	Accuracy	Precision	Sensitivity	F1-score
<i>KNN</i>	0.6585	0.6333	0.8636	0.7308
<i>NB</i>	0.8293	0.7778	0.9545	0.8571